

RAM-SCB Simulations

This archive contains data files from two simulations of the Ring current Atmosphere interactions Model with Self Consistent magnetic field (RAM-SCB). The files are:

- One CDF file which contains the OMNI data.
- Six CDF files which contain the precipitation data of electrons and protons obtained from the NOAA's Polar Orbiting Environmental Satellites (POES).
- Two log files, one for each simulation, which contain the Dst calculated from RAM-SCB.
- In the FLC folder, one plasmopause boundary output file which contains the footprint of plasmopause on the equatorial plane and ionosphere, index 0 from noon.
- In the FLC folder, three diffusion coefficients output files (FLC_coeff_*_d20130317_t103000.dat) associated with FLC scattering, which contain the particles' energy, pitch angle, particle gyroradius, the FLC radius, Epsil, tau_bounce and diffusion coefficient Daa.
- In the FLC folder, the Electron, H⁺ ions, He⁺ ions and O⁺ ions precipitation output files at different times (PrecipFlux_diff_*_t*.dat), which contain the location at ionosphere (theta and phi), particles energy and differential number flux calculated from the RAM.
- In the FLC folder and WithoutFLC folder, the H⁺ ions and O⁺ ions precipitation output files at different times (PrecipFlux_atSCBEquator_*_t*.dat), which contain the location at the equatorial plane (radius and azimuthal angle), particles energy and flux calculated from the RAM.

These simulations were performed for, and used in the paper “The effects of field line curvature (FLC) scattering on ring current dynamics and ionospheric electrodynamics” by Yu, Y., Tian, X., V.K. Jordanova, submitted to Journal of Geophysical Research - Space Physics, 2020.